

Comparative performance evaluation of conventional and two-phase hydrophobic stirred tank reactors for methane abatement: Mass Transfer and Biological Considerations

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3 **Comparative performance evaluation of conventional and two-phase**
4 **hydrophobic stirred tank reactors for methane abatement: Mass Transfer**
5 **and Biological Considerations**
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Abstract

This study demonstrated for the first time the capability of methanotrophs to grow inside silicone oil (SO200) and identified the optimum cultivation conditions for enrichment of hydrophobic methanotrophs (high dilution rates (D) and low CH₄ transfer rates). The potential of the hydrophobic methanotrophs enriched was assessed in a single-phase stirred tank reactor (1P-STR) and in a two-phase stirred tank reactor (2P-STR). Different operational conditions were systematically evaluated in both reactors (SO200 fractions of 30 and 60 %, stirring rates of 250 and 500 rpm, and D of 0.1-0.35 day⁻¹ with and without biomass retention). The results showed that the TPPB only supported a superior CH₄ abatement performance compared to the 1P-STR (40% enhancement at 250 rpm and 25% enhancement at 500 rpm) at a D of 0.3 day⁻¹ due to the retention of the biocatalytic activity inside the SO200, while the 1P-STR achieved higher elimination capacities (EC up to ≈3 times) than the TPPB under the rest of conditions tested (EC_{max} = 91.1 g m⁻³ h⁻¹). Furthermore, the microscopic examination and DGGE-sequencing of the communities showed that the presence of SO200 influenced the microbial population structure, impacting on bacterial biodiversity and favoring the growth of methanotrophs such as *Methylosarcina*.

Keywords:

Two-phase partitioning bioreactors, CH₄ abatement, hydrophobic bacteria, methanotrophs, mass transfer limitation.

1. Introduction

Methane (CH₄), with a global warming potential 34 times greater than that of CO₂ (over a 100-y window), is the second most important greenhouse gas (GHG) (IPPC 2013). The concentration of CH₄ increases at a yearly rate of 0.3-1 %, mainly due to anthropogenic activities (natural gas and petroleum systems, enteric fermentation, landfills, coal mining, waste management and energy production) (European Environmental Agency, 2015; United

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3 States Environmental Protection Agency, 2015). More than 56 % of anthropogenic CH₄
4 emissions contain this GHG at concentrations below 3 %, where current CH₄ treatment
5 methods are neither efficient nor cost-effective (Avalos Ramirez et al., 2012). Dilute CH₄
6 emissions (< 3%) are typically found in old landfills (0–20%), in ventilated coal mines (0.1–
7 1%), in covered liquid manure storage tanks (0–3%) and confined cattle operations (<1%)
8 (Estrada et al., 2014). This situation has encouraged both political initiatives and an intensive
9 research on novel strategies for CH₄ abatement (European Environmental Agency, 2015).
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19 Conventional biological off-gas treatment technologies such as biofilters, biotrickling filters,
20 stirred tank bioreactors and airlift bioreactors are based on the biocatalytic activity of
21 specialized bacteria or fungi, and if properly tailored, they can be a cost efficient and
22 environmentally friendly solution for the treatment of diluted CH₄ emissions from abandoned
23 landfills, ventilated coal mines, manure storage tanks and confined cattle operations (López et
24 al., 2013). However, these technologies are limited by the low water solubility of CH₄ when
25 applied to CH₄ abatement, which hampers its gas-liquid transport to the methane oxidizing
26 bacteria (MOB) and limits the overall CH₄ treatment performance of conventional
27 biotechnologies (López et al., 2014). Two-phase partitioning bioreactors (TPPBs) have been
28 proposed as an alternative to improve the removal of scarcely soluble atmospheric pollutants.
29 This technology is based on the addition to the bioreactor of a non-toxic, non-volatile and
30 non-biodegradable non-aqueous phase (NAP) with a high affinity for the target pollutant and
31 a low vapor pressure (Daugulis, 2001). Strategy that has been successfully applied to the
32 treatment of hydrophobic volatile organic compounds (VOCs) such as toluene (Daugulis and
33 Boudreau, 2003) and hexane (Hernández et al., 2010; Muñoz et al., 2013).
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53 In the particular case of CH₄ biodegradation, the use of liquid NAPs has been tested in
54 different bioreactor configurations with promising results (Avalos Ramirez et al., 2012;
55 Kraakman et al., 2011; Lebrero et al., 2015; Rocha-Rios et al., 2009). However, there is still
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3 limited information about the mechanisms underlying the beneficial effects of NAPs at
4 different operational conditions and the results were sometimes contradictory. In this context,
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7 the use of hydrophobic methanotrophs capable of growing inside the NAP could support a
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10 direct pollutant uptake and improve the overall CH₄ abatement capacity of the bioreactor. For
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12 instance, recent studies addressing the biodegradation of VOCs in TPPBs operated with the
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14 biomass growing inside the NAP reported significant increases in the elimination capacity
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16 (EC) under steady state operation (Hernandez et al., 2012).
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19 Unfortunately, the role and mechanisms of the confinement of methanotrophic bacterial
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21 activity inside the NAP on bioreactor performance and cell viability when MOB grow inside
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23 the NAP remains still unclear (Lebrero et al., 2015; Rocha-Rios et al., 2009).
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26 The present work aimed at exploring the potential and optimizing the operational conditions
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28 of TPPBs operated with hydrophobic bacterial communities for CH₄ abatement. First, the
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30 culture conditions resulting in the enrichment of hydrophobic methanotrophs were
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32 established, thus confirming the activity and viability of MOB in the NAP. Secondly, a
33
34 systematic comparison of the performance of a conventional aqueous-phase stirred tank
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36 bioreactor (1P-STR) and a two-liquid phase stirred tank bioreactor (2P-STR) using silicone
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38 oil 200 cSt (SO200) as the model NAP was carried out. Both reactors were inoculated with
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40 the enriched MOB and operated with a special focus on the study of process microbiology
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42 and on the identification of the limiting step under each operational condition tested.
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46 47 **2. Materials and methods**

48 49 *2.1. Chemicals and mineral salt medium*

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52 The mineral salt medium (MSM) used during the enrichment of hydrophobic methanotrophs,
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54 as well as during bioreactor operation, was a modified Brunner medium containing 25 μM
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56 Cu²⁺ and prepared according to López et al. (2014). All chemicals and reagents were
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3 purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) with a purity higher than 99.0%. CH₄ was
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5 obtained from Abelló-Linde, S.A. (Barcelona, Spain) with a purity higher than 99.5 %.
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7 Silicone oil 200 cSt (SO200) was procured from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). The CH₄
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9 partition coefficient in SO200 accounts for 2 ± 0.1 compared to 30 in water at 25 °C (Rocha-
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11 Ríos et al., 2011) and the Hildebrand Solubility Parameters of CH₄ and SO200 are also very
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13 similar (11.0 MPa^{1/2} and 14.9 MPa^{1/2}, respectively), which confirmed the miscibility of
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15 both compounds, ergo the high solubility of methane in SO200 (Rocha Rios et al., 2011;
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17 Bacon et al., 2014). Due to these characteristics, SO200 was here used for enhancing the
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19 mass transport of CH₄ from the gas to the aqueous phase (whereas SO200 is also suitable for
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21 detoxification, this application was not the aim of the present study). Moreover, SO200 has
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23 been proven to support microbial growth inside, which enhances the biodegradation
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25 performance of the two-phase partitioning bioreactor due to the higher VOC and O₂
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27 concentration in the NAP, besides being biocompatible, non-biodegradable, non-hazardous
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29 and odorless. Despite silicone oil has certain drawbacks as a transfer vector, since it is
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31 relatively expensive and its recovery may increase process cost, it constitutes, to the best of
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33 our knowledge, one of the few solvents evaluated that gathers all the above mentioned
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35 properties (Muñoz et al., 2014).
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41 *2.2. Microorganisms and enrichment procedure*

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44 Fresh aerobic settled activated sludge ($\approx 6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) from a denitrification-nitrification
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46 wastewater treatment plant (Valladolid, Spain) and fresh cow manure from a dairy farm
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48 (Cantabria, Spain) were used as inocula for the enrichment of hydrophobic methanotrophs.
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50 Briefly, a 10× dilution of the cow manure sample in MSM was mixed with activated sludge
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52 (50%/50% v/v). The enrichment was carried out for 45 days in six glass bottles (1.2 L)
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54 containing 100 mL of MSM and 50 mL of SO200, and provided with 10 mL of the inoculum
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56 above described. The bottles were closed with gas-tight butyl septa and plastic screw caps. O₂
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3 was supplied via air flushing of the bottle headspace prior to pure CH₄ injection to obtain a
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5 headspace concentration of 55 g CH₄ m⁻³. This experimental protocol was daily repeated to
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7 restore O₂ and CH₄ headspace concentrations since CH₄ was totally depleted in 24 h. Cultures
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9 were grown at three different aqueous phase dilution rates (D = 0.12, 0.55 and 0.70 day⁻¹)
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11 under two different magnetic agitation conditions (300 and 650 rpm) (Table 1) and daily
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13 monitored for CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations in the headspace. The two MOB cultures
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15 exhibiting the best growth inside SO200 (test series 2 and 3, Table 1) were chosen as inocula
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17 for 1P-STR and 2P-STR operation.
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21 <Table I>
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24 During the 45 days of culture enrichment, random liquid samples from all 6 bottles were
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26 drawn to microscopically image the SO200, aqueous phase and SO200-aqueous interphase. In
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28 addition, vital and dead bacteria inside the SO200 were identified.
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31 2.3 Experimental set-up and operation 32 33

34 Two 1-L jacketed stirred tank reactors (Afora S.A., Spain) were used for continuous CH₄
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36 abatement. The MOB enriched in TS2 and TS3 were mixed (50/50% v/v) and used as the
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38 inoculum for both reactors. The control 1P-STR was operated in the absence of SO200, filled
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40 with 700 mL of MSM and 300 mL of the aqueous phase of the hydrophobic bacterial
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42 inoculum. The 2P-STR was initially filled with 500 mL of MSM, 200 mL of new SO200, 100
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44 mL of the organic phase of the inoculum and 200 mL of its respective aqueous phase. A 0.1 L
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46 min⁻¹ CH₄ laden air emission containing 25.9 ± 2.1 g CH₄ m⁻³ (≈ 4%; concentration within
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48 the range of diluted CH₄ emissions typically found in abandoned landfills, coal mines,
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50 manure storage tanks and cattle farms) corresponding to a methane load of 150 g m⁻³ h⁻¹
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52 (loads similar to those typically applied in conventional biofilters and biotrickling filters
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54 devoted to the treatment of CH₄; Nikiema et al., 2007) was fed into the 1P- and 2P-STRs via
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3 10 µm porous stainless steel diffusers located at the bottom of the reactors. The stream was
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5 obtained by mixing a pure CH₄ stream (controlled by means of a mass flow controller,
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7 Aalborg, USA) with a pre-humidified air flow, resulting in a gas empty bed residence time
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9 (EBRT) of 10 min. Six different sets of operational conditions were tested in both reactors. In
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11 the first and second stages (S1C and S2C in 1P-STR; S1 and S2 in 2P-STR) the stirring rate
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13 was fixed at 500 rpm, the dilution rate was 0.35 day⁻¹ and the biomass drawn with the
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15 effluent was returned to the reactor following a total cell recycling strategy (the aqueous
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17 cultivation broth drawn was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 5 min, the biomass pellet re-
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19 suspended in fresh MSM and returned to the bioreactor). This operation mode provided
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21 enough nutrients for microbial growth and avoided the accumulation of toxic inhibitory
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23 metabolites while efficiently retaining biomass in the system at high concentrations. In 2P-
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25 STR, 300 mL of MSM were replaced by fresh SO200 in S2 in order to increase the SO200
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27 fraction from 30 to 60% v/v. The agitation rate was decreased to 250 rpm in stages S3 and
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29 S3C. In 2P-STR, 300 mL of MSM were replaced by fresh SO200 in S2 in order to increase
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31 the SO200 fraction from 30 to 60% v/v. The agitation rate was decreased to 250 rpm in stages
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33 S3 and S3C, while in stages S4 and S4C the dilution rate was decreased to 0.10 day⁻¹ by daily
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35 replacement of 100 mL of aqueous cultivation broth with fresh MSM without biomass return.
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37 A slight increase in the dilution rate to 0.30 day⁻¹ was implemented in stages S5 and S5C,
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39 while in the final stages S6 and S6C the stirring rate was increased back to 500 rpm (Table
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48 <Table II>
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51 Both systems were operated at 25 °C and a pH of 7.5 ± 0.3 was maintained via daily
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53 replacement of the MSM. Distilled water (50 mL) was added weekly to compensate water
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55 losses by evaporation. The NAP was daily recovered from the withdrawn liquid and returned
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57 to the reactor in order to maintain the NAP/ MSM ratio corresponding to each operational
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3 stage. The elimination capacity ($\text{g m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$), removal efficiency (RE, %) and volumetric CO_2
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5 production rate (TPCO_2 , $\text{g m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$) were evaluated in both reactors. An operational steady
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7 state was achieved when neither the EC nor RE deviated $>10\%$ from the mean (only average
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9 values of stages S1 and S2 with deviations $\sim 15\%$ are shown due to the highly fluctuating
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11 performance of the TPPB). Gas samples for CH_4 and CO_2 determination were periodically
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13 taken from the sampling ports located at the inlet and outlet of the bioreactors using gas-tight
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15 syringes (HAMILTON, Australia). Aqueous samples of 20 mL were also periodically drawn
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17 to measure the biomass concentration (as total suspended solids, TSS). Biomass samples
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19 from the enriched hydrophobic inoculum and from the aqueous cultivation broth at the end of
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21 each steady state were drawn to determine the microbial population structure by denaturing
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23 gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE)-sequencing.
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27 28 *2.4 Identification of mass transfer limitations*

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31 A mass transfer test was carried out at the end of each steady state in order to elucidate the
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33 limiting step during CH_4 biodegradation under the experimental conditions evaluated. In this
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35 regard, if the concentration of methane in the inlet emission increased by a factor of 2, the
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37 mass flow of methane potentially available for the microbial community also increased by a
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39 factor of 2. Under a microbial activity limiting scenario, not enough bacteria would be
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41 available to degrade this extra methane load and therefore the EC and TPCO_2 would remain
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43 constant (similar to the EC and TPCO_2 before the increase in the IL). However, if the process
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45 was limited by the mass transfer of the substrate to the community, the EC and the TPCO_2
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47 would eventually increase by a factor of 2 as a result of the higher CH_4 concentration gradient
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49 available for CH_4 mass transfer and the availability of a microbial community active enough
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51 to cope with this additional CH_4 load. For this purpose the inlet CH_4 concentration was
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53 increased from $27.9 \pm 0.9 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ to $52.1 \pm 1.6 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ for 6 h and the concomitant change in EC
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55 and CO_2 production was periodically recorded (Lebrero et al., 2015).
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3 In addition, the dissolved CH₄ concentration in the aqueous phase was determined after the
4 mass transfer test in S4C and S5C to confirm the biological limitation. For this purpose, 5 mL
5 of cultivation broth were injected in a 15 mL vial closed with a butyl septum, sealed with an
6 aluminum cap and supplemented with 0.1 mL of H₂SO₄ to stop biological activity. The vial
7 was immediately shaken vigorously and allowed to equilibrate for 2 h at 25 °C prior to the
8 determination of the CH₄ headspace concentration (Frutos et al., 2014). The aqueous CH₄
9 concentration was then calculated using the individual gas and liquid volumes and a Henry's
10 law constant for CH₄ of 30 at 25 °C (Sander, 1999).
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20 21 *2.5. Analytical procedures*

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24 CH₄ and CO₂ gas concentrations were determined in a Bruker 430 GC-TCD according to
25 Lopez et al. (2014). TSS were measured according to Standard Methods (American Water
26 Works Association, 2012). Vital and dead bacteria inside the SO200 were identified using the
27 LIVE/DEAD BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit (L13152). The SO200, aqueous phase and
28 SO200-aqueous interphase were imaged in a Leica DM4000B microscope equipped with a
29 Leica DFC300FX.
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38 *2.6. Structure of the enriched communities*

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41 The total DNA was extracted using the Fast® DNA Spin Kit for Soil handbook (MP
42 Biomedicals, LLC). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) products of the bacterial 16S rDNA
43 fragments from the samples were separated by DGGE according to Roest et al. (2005). Gels
44 were stained with GelRed Nucleic Acid Gel Stain (biotium) for 1 h. Specific PCR-DGGE
45 bands were manually excised from the gel, resuspended in 50 mL of sterile water and
46 incubated at 60 °C for 1 hour. The last PCR cycle was performed without the GC-clamp
47 attached to the forward primer 968-F. The resulting PCR products were sent to Secugen S.L.
48 (Madrid, Spain) for nucleotide sequencing. The taxonomic position of the sequenced DGGE
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bands was obtained using the RDP classifier tool (70% confidence level) (Wang et al., 2007). The closest matches to each band were obtained using the BLAST search tool from the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (McGinnis and Madden, 2004). The absence of chimeras in the sequences was assessed using the DECIPHER search tool (Wright et al., 2012) before deposit in the GenBank Data Library. The DGGE patterns obtained were compared using the GelCompar IITM software (Applied Maths BVBA, Sint-Martens-Latem, Belgium) to determine the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and the Shannon-Wiener diversity index (Hs) according to Lopez et al. (2014). The DNA sequences obtained were used to construct phylogenetic trees by using the ClustalX2.1 and MEGA 6.06 program package. The phylogenetic trees were constructed using the neighbor-joining method (1000-fold bootstrap analysis) (Hall, 2013).

2.7. Statistical analysis

The statistical data analysis was performed using SPSS 20.0 (IBM). The occurrence of significant differences in the steady states achieved in both bioreactors operated under the same operating conditions were analyzed by ANOVA and post-hoc analysis. A Levene test was used to study homoscedasticity. Differences were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Enrichment of hydrophobic bacteria

The enrichment strategy was based on the exposure of microorganisms to different effective CH_4 mass transfer rates (determined by the stirring rate) under similar CH_4 headspace concentrations, and to different dilution rates (D) in the aqueous phase, which selectively washed-out MOB growing in the aqueous-phase (Table 1). The lowest stirring rate (300 rpm), which supported both a limited transfer of CH_4 to the microbial community and a reduced SO_2 dispersion, favored microbial growth inside SO_2 (microscopic

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3 observations, Figure 1). However, the MOB enriched at 650 rpm did not grow inside the
4 SO200 since the higher agitation rates likely resulted in a higher CH₄ mass transfer into the
5 aqueous phase (where nutrients were easily available), and therefore the environmental
6 pressure for bacteria to migrate inside the organic phase disappeared. A higher D also
7 promoted microbial growth in the organic phase. Thus, the first hydrophobic microorganisms
8 in cultures at 300 rpm were observed by day 15 at 0.70 day⁻¹ (TS3), by day 21 at 0.55 day⁻¹
9 (TS2), and by day 38 at 0.12 day⁻¹ (TS1). The MOB found inside the NAP grew in the form
10 of aggregates (Figure 1). A similar growth pattern has been reported in previous studies for
11 different NAPs, where bacteria were able to accumulate in the aqueous-NAP interphase and
12 grow inside NAPs forming aggregates (Fu et al., 2015; Han et al., 2009b; Yamashita et al.,
13 2007). Moreover, McLeod and Daugulis (2005) observed that certain hydrophobic bacteria
14 formed aggregates in the aqueous phase instead of inside the NAP. Overall, cell aggregates
15 offer an advantage to colonize a new habitat and to enhance the environmental quality of
16 hostile habitats (Langer et al., 2014; Lazarova and Manem, 1995). In our particular case, the
17 main factor likely promoting the formation of aggregates inside SO200 was the limitation in
18 nutrients or water activity inside the NAP, since cell aggregation may have supported the
19 preservation of the aqueous niches required for the growth of *Methylosarcina*. In fact, the
20 entrapment of MSM droplets inside NAPs has been empirically proven (Cordiki et al., 2012).
21 However, the mechanisms that allow some bacteria to grow inside the NAP still remain
22 unclear, and more research in this field is needed.

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50 Previous studies reported cells growing inside other NAPs using fluorescence staining
51 (McLeod and Daugulis (2005). However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study
52 in literature demonstrating that the bacteria observed inside SO200 were viable cells. Hence,
53 fluorescence in-situ hybridization of the cells present in the SO200, in the aqueous phase and
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3 in the interphase showed that those bacteria were alive (fluorescent green staining) (Figure
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5 1b), thus confirming that SO₂O₀ was non-toxic for the MOB.
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8 3.2 Comparative evaluation of a 1P-STR and a 2P-STR for CH₄ abatement 9

10 Six operational stages were evaluated in both reactors to compare their performance and to
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12 determine the optimal operational parameters for continuous CH₄ abatement.
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16 <Figure 2>
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19 On day 14, the first steady state was reached in 1P-STR (S1C/S2C, Table 2), with average
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21 ECs and REs of $91.1 \pm 1.9 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $57.0 \pm 1.0 \%$, respectively. On the contrary, the ECs
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23 obtained in the 2P-STR during the first 27 days were highly variable, exhibiting average
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25 values of 38.0 ± 5.8 and $46.0 \pm 3.6 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and REs of 27.1 ± 3.5 and $34.9 \pm 4.5 \%$ in S1
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27 and S2, respectively (Figure 2). Surprisingly, the increase in SO₂O₀ fraction from 30 to 60 %
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29 did not significantly affect the performance of the 2P-STR. The results of the mass transfer
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31 limitation tests in these stages (S1C/S2C, S1 and S2) revealed that a $\times 1.9 \pm 0.03$ increase in
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33 the inlet load resulted in both a $\times 1.6 \pm 0.02$ increase in the EC and a concomitant increase of
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35 $\times 1.3 \pm 0.03$ in the TPCO₂ (Figure 3a). Therefore, the higher concentration gradient at
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37 increasing CH₄ concentration in the gas phase supported higher ECs, thus confirming the
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39 mass transfer limitations regardless of the presence and fraction of the NAP. During stages
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41 S1C/S2C, S1 and S2, an average TSS concentration of $5.6 \pm 1.3 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ was recorded in the 1P-
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43 STR while in the 2P-STR, the aqueous TSS concentrations oscillated within a similar range
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45 ($7.3 \pm 2.4 \text{ g L}^{-1}$). Microscopic observations revealed that biomass grew mainly in the aqueous
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47 phase of both reactors, supporting a high biodiversity during these stages (diverse protozoans,
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49 including *Vorticella*, *Opercularia* or *Euplotes*, and bacteria were identified).
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55 The agitation rate was decreased to 250 rpm on day 33, which mediated in the 1P-STR (stage
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57 S3C) a decrease in the steady state EC to $55.5 \pm 1.6 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and in the RE to $34.9 \pm 1.1 \%$.
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3 The EC and RE in the 2P-STR operated at 250 rpm (stage S3) were $\times 1.8$ times lower than
4 those reached in the 1P-STR. Unfortunately, a significant deterioration in the performance of
5 the 2P-STR at this lower agitation rate could not be confirmed based on the high variations in
6 EC and RE recorded in the two first operational stages. As expected, the mass transfer tests
7 confirmed that both reactors remained mass transfer-limited during stages S3C and S3.
8 Indeed, a $\times 2.0 \pm 0.05$ increase in CH_4 inlet load resulted in increases of $\times 1.9 \pm 0.3$ and $\times 1.6 \pm$
9 0.4 in the EC and the TPCO_2 , respectively (average test results of both reactors). The
10 maximum TSS concentration in the aqueous phase was reached in this third stage due to
11 biomass retention ($10.6 \pm 0.9 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ and $10.3 \pm 1.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in 1P-STR and 2P-STR, respectively).
12 The increasing biomass concentrations observed in stages 1, 2 and 3 suggested the use of
13 methane for cell maintenance purposes as well as cell growth. Similarly to stages S1 and S2,
14 the microscopic images showed that most microorganisms grew preferentially in the aqueous
15 phase. These results supported those obtained in the enrichment tests, where low dilution
16 rates did not favor the abundance of bacteria able to grow inside the SO200.

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35 Stages S4C and S4 were characterized by process operation with no biomass return at a D of
36 0.1 day^{-1} . No statistical differences existed between the ECs and REs recorded in both
37 reactors during this stage (according to the one-way ANOVA test combined with a Games-
38 Howell post hoc analysis, $p < 0.05$). The EC obtained decreased to $31.2 \pm 1.6 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and the
39 RE to $19.1 \pm 1.6 \%$ in the 1P-STR. However, the average EC and RE recorded in the 2P-STR
40 did not show statistical differences with those recorded in S3 ($30.0 \pm 3.1 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $20.6 \pm$
41 2.1%) (Figure 2). A biological limitation was identified in the 1P-STR at a TSS
42 concentration of $2.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, since a 2.1-fold increase in the CH_4 inlet load resulted in
43 negligible variations in EC and TPCO_2 (Figure 3b). This biological limitation was further
44 confirmed by the relatively high CH_4 concentration measured in the aqueous phase (0.43 g m^{-3}),
45 which clearly showed that CH_4 was transferred to the aqueous phase at higher rates than
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3 its microbial consumption. However, and despite the decrease in aqueous TSS concentration
4 to $4.5 \pm 0.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in the 2P-STR due to daily biomass removal, the mass transfer test
5 confirmed that the TPPB was still mass transfer limited, and therefore the concentrations of
6 CH_4 in both liquid phase were theoretically $0 \text{ mg CH}_4 \text{ L}^{-1}$ (otherwise the system would be
7 limited by microbial activity). This discrepancy between both reactors can be explained by
8 the fact that SO200 prevented the washout of the biomass entrapped inside the NAP in the
9 2P-STR. In this context, the microscopic observations (Figure 4a, d) revealed that a new
10 population of sarcine-shape bacteria established inside the SO200 during S4. It is important
11 to notice that the possibility of all methane being sequestered inside the organic phase was
12 unlikely in the particular case of SO200 and CH_4 based on the moderate CH_4 partition
13 coefficient of CH_4 in silicone oil (Déziel et al., 1999).
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28 <Figure 3>
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31 In this context, the dilution rate was increased to 0.3 day^{-1} during S5 and S5C in order to
32 further promote the growth of hydrophobic bacteria inside the NAP. The steady ECs reported
33 were $29.7 \pm 1.5 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $52.5 \pm 2.8 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the 1P-STR and 2P-STR, corresponding
34 to REs of $20.3 \pm 1.6 \%$ in the 1P-STR and $33.8 \pm 1.4 \%$ in the 2P-STR. No statistical
35 differences were observed in the performance of the 1P-STR when compared with the
36 previous stage S4C. However during S5, the 2P-STR achieved ECs and REs 1.6 times higher
37 than in S4. The lower biomass concentration ($0.9 \pm 0.1 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) imposed by the higher dilution
38 rate supported the occurrence of biological limitation in the 1P-STR. Thus, a $\times 1.9$ increase in
39 the CH_4 inlet load did not result in a significant increase in the EC or the TPCO_2 in the
40 control reactor. On the contrary, the 2P-STR continued to be mass transfer limited despite the
41 aqueous concentration of biomass decreased to $1.9 \pm 0.7 \text{ g L}^{-1}$. In this regard, microscopic
42 observations confirmed the active bacterial growth inside the SO200 (Figure 4b).
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<Figure 4>

Finally, the agitation rate was increased from 250 to 500 rpm at a D of 0.3 day⁻¹ during S6 and S6C. Both the EC ($41.3 \pm 0.8 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and RE ($24.2 \pm 0.8 \%$) increased compared to the previous stage in the 1P-STR. However, the EC and RE ($54.4 \pm 0.4 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, 32.2 %) recorded in the 2P-STR did not show statistical differences with S5. The mass transfer experiments showed that both reactors were mass transfer limited during stage 6. The increase in the stirring rate resulted in an increase in the TSS concentration up to $1.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in the 1P-STR likely as a result of the higher CH₄ mass transport to the microbial community. This increase in biomass concentration shifted process limitation from microbial activity to mass transport. The average aqueous TSS concentration in the 2P-STR was not significantly different from that in S5 ($1.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$). The steady biomass concentrations reached in stages 4, 5 and 6 were the result of the equilibrium between cell growth and cell evacuation under steady state conditions. The system never operated under completely cell maintenance as previously observed by Daugulis and co-workers in TPPBs (Boudreau and Daugulis, 2006). According to microscopic observations, bacteria actively grew inside the SO₂O₀ and NAP droplets were surrounded by bacterial flocs (Figure 4c). The surprising absence of performance enhancement in the 2P-STR despite the expected increase in CH₄ mass transfer at higher agitation rates might be due to the fact that CH₄ diffusion inside the SO₂O₀ rather than gas-liquid mass transport was limiting CH₄ abatement during stage 6.

3.3 Microbial population diversity and community profile

<Figure 5>

The enriched hydrophobic inoculum showed the lowest number and evenness of species among the analyzed samples according to its low Shannon Wiener diversity index ($H=1.4$) (Fig. 5). This fact was mainly due to the selective cultivation conditions of the inoculum

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3 carried out during the enrichment stage. CH₄ was the only carbon source and the high dilution
4 rate applied washout the majority of bacteria not associated with SO₂O₀. The biodiversity
5 increased over time in the 1P-STR, with *H* values ranging from 1.9 to 2.2. In the 2P-STR,
6 there was an initial biodiversity raise, with the maximum *H* found in S3 when biomass was
7 returned to the reactor and the aqueous TSS concentration was 10.3 ± 1.6 g L⁻¹. Despite this
8 initial increase, the biodiversity decreased throughout the following stages probably due to
9 bacterial specialization and biomass washout, with *H* values of 2.5, 2.4 and 2 in stages S4, S5
10 and S6, respectively. At this point it is important to remark that mixed samples (including
11 both NAP and aqueous phase) were analyzed. The diversity values obtained in this study
12 were within the range previously reported for long-term cultures exposed to diluted CH₄
13 emissions (Estrada et al., 2014; Lebrero et al., 2015). Relatively low *H* values, compared to
14 samples from other environments exposed to varied energy and rich carbon sources, were
15 expected since CH₄ was the only carbon and energy source provided.

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Despite the high similarity found between the inoculum and the communities established in the final stage of the 2P-STR (85.5 %), the similarity obtained between stage S3 and the inoculum was considerably lower (40.7 %). This demonstrated that the enrichment with SO₂O₀ determined a common specialization strategy that favored only a few hydrophobic MOB populations, while supporting a lower bacterial biodiversity. In the particular case of the 1P-STR, a significant shift in microbial population was observed, with a gradual decrease in the similarity with the inoculum from stage S3C onward (90.0, 76.7, 68.9 and 55.3 %). A low similarity was also observed between S6 and S6C (52.2 %), which confirmed that SO₂O₀ had a clear influence on the bacterial population structure.

<Figure 6>

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3 The DGGE-sequencing results (Figure 6) showed that all bands obtained belonged to two
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5 phyla according to the RDP classifier tool: the phylum *Proteobacteria* (bands 1 to 18) and the
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7 phylum *Verrucomicrobia* (bands 19 and 20) (Table I, supporting information). Most bands
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9 (5-18) were classified into the *Gammaproteobacteria* class. All methanotrophs identified
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11 belonged to the *Gammaproteobacteria* class were classified as type I and X MOB. The MOB
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13 genera found were *Methylomonas*, *Methylobacter*, *Methylomicrobium*, *Methylosarcina* and
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15 *Methylococcus* ((Hanson and Hanson, 1996; Kao et al., 2004; Wise et al., 1999), which have
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17 been previously identified in bioreactors devoted to CH₄ treatment (Estrada et al., 2014;
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19 López et al., 2014). The genus *Methylomonas* (bands 5, 7 and 11) was the only methanotroph
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21 detected by DGGE in the inoculum, and dominated the population of both bioreactors along
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23 the entire experimental period (likely due to the high growth rates of this MOB).
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25 Interestingly, the genus *Methylosarcina* (bands 13, 14, 15 and 16) was only detected in the
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27 2P-STR from stage S4 to S6, which agreed with the microscopic observations of the NAP
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29 conducted during these operational stages (Figure 4). The genus *Methylosarcina* has been
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31 previously detected in STR bioreactors treating diluted emissions of CH₄ in the absence of
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33 SO₂00 (López et al., 2014). In addition to MOB, bacteria from the genus *Hypomicrobium*
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35 (band 2-3; a common methylotroph that utilizes the methanol from CH₄ oxidation (Hanson
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37 and Hanson, 1996)) were present both in the inoculum and in the cultivation broth of the
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39 1P,2P-STR regardless of the operational conditions evaluated (Calhoun and King, 1998; Han
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41 et al., 2009a; López et al., 2014).
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48 Other non-methanotrophic heterotrophic genera such as *Dokdonella* (band 18), *Pseudomonas*
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50 (band 17) and *Spartobacteria* (bands 19 and 20), which have been retrieved in two-phase
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52 partitioning biotrickling filters treating CH₄ (Lebrero et al., 2015), were detected in the 2P-
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54 STR during the stage with the highest diversity (S3). Nevertheless, these microorganisms
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56 gradually disappeared due to MSM exchange, while those that occupied the SO₂00 protected
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3 niche created a reservoir for stable colonization. On the other hand, the genus *Stappia* (band
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5 4), a non- methanotrophic versatile organism which occupy several niches and participate in
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7 CO oxidation and denitrification (Weber and King, 2007) was identified in every stage in the
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9 2P-STR and in S3C, S4C and S6C in the 1P-STR (Veillette et al., 2011).
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11 12 **4. Conclusion** 13

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15 This study confirmed, for the first time, the ability of hydrophobic methanotrophs to grow
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17 and maintain their viability inside a NAP. High dilution rates together with low CH₄ transfer
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19 rates were identified as the best enrichment conditions for hydrophobic methanotrophs.
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21 Under continuous bioreactor operation, this study demonstrated that the addition of a non-
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23 aqueous phase (60% v/v SO200) at high biomass concentrations (mediated by biomass
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25 retention) did not result in an enhancement in methane abatement compared to a conventional
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27 1P-STR. However, process operation at high dilution rates promoted the washout of biomass
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29 in the aqueous phase and the accumulation of hydrophobic methanotrophs in the NAP, which
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31 resulted in a superior performance of the 2P-STR. The 2P-STR was always mass transfer
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33 limited, while in the absence of biomass retention at low stirring rates (conditions typically
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35 encountered under full-scale operation) the 1P-STR was limited by biological activity. Both
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37 the microscopic observations and the DGGE analysis showed that the presence of SO200
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39 severely influenced the community structure and bacterial biodiversity. Finally, the
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41 investigation of new NAPs with higher affinities for CH₄, and the elucidation of the
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43 differential microbial growth and specific strategies that enable some MOB to be viable
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45 inside the NAP will be of major interest for the optimization of TPPBs with the biocatalytic
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47 activity confined in the NAP.
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Figure 1.

Figure 1. Microscopic images of the enriched bacteria in TS2 (300 rpm, $D= 0.55 \text{ day}^{-1}$) using a) a phase contrast microscope Leica DM40000b AT 40 \times magnification (focused on the organic phase to identify microbial growth inside the NAP) and b) a Leica DM40000b AT fluorescence microscope 20 \times magnification and specific filters sets for alive bacteria (SYTO@9 green-fluorescent nucleic acid stain) and dead bacteria (propidium iodide red-fluorescent nucleic acid stain).

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Average EC in the 1P-STR (black) and 2P-STR (scratched). Vertical bars represent standard deviations from replicates during steady state in each operational stage. Columns with different letters were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3.

Figure 3. Time course of CH₄ concentration (black continuous line), the EC (▲, dashed line) and the CO₂ production rate (●, dotted line) during the mass transfer limitation test in a) S1C/S2C (mass transfer limitation scenario), b) S4C (biological limitation scenario).

Figure 4.

Figure 4. Microscopic images using a phase contrast microscope Leica DM40000b AT of the hydrophobic MOB established in a) S4 (20× magnification), b) S5 (20× magnification) c) S6 (40× magnification) and d) S4 (100× magnification).

Figure 5

Fig.5: DGGE profile of the main bacterial communities present in: the 2P-STR (S3, S4, S5, S6), Initial Inoculum (I) and in the 1P-STR (S3C, S4C, S5C, S6C). The Shannon-Wiener diversity indexes are indicated in the upper part of the gel. The sequenced bands are indicated by “▶” and the corresponding number of each band.

Figure 6.

Figure 6. Bacterial phylogenetic tree based on neighbor-joining analysis of the 16S rRNA sequences from the enriched populations of both reactors by PCR-DGGE and their closest relatives (similarity > 96%) in GenBank obtained by the Blast search tool. Accession numbers are indicated. Numbers on the nodes indicate bootstrap values (1000 replicates). The scale bar indicates 10% sequence difference.

Table I: Cultivation conditions during hydrophobic microbial community enrichments

Test series (TS)	Dilution rate (day ⁻¹)	Stirring rate (rpm)	Presence of hydrophobic bacteria (day of appearance)
TS1	0.12	300	Yes (day 38)
TS2	0.55	300	Yes (day 21)
TS3	0.70	300	Yes (day 15)
TS4	0.12	650	No
TS5	0.55	650	No
TS6	0.70	650	No

Table II: Operational stages in the aqueous-phase stirred tank reactor (1P-STR) and in the two-phase stirred tank reactor (2P-STR).

	Stage (operating days)	SO ₂ O ₀	Dilution rate (day ⁻¹)	Biomass return	Stirring rate (rpm)
1P-STR	S1C/S2C (14-29)		0.35	yes	500
	S3C (33-47)		0.35	yes	250
	S4C (68-83)		0.10	no	250
	S5C (105-120)		0.30	no	250
	S6C (130-149)		0.30	no	500
2P-STR	S1 (3-19)	30%	0.35	yes	500
	S2 (20-27)	60%	0.35	yes	500
	S3 (30-45)	60%	0.35	yes	250
	S4 (50-65)	60%	0.10	no	250
	S5 (80-97)	60%	0.30	no	250
	S6 (104-124)	60%	0.30	no	500

Microscopic images of the enriched bacteria in TS2 (300 rpm, $D = 0.55 \text{ day}^{-1}$) using a) a phase contrast microscope Leica DM40000b AT 40x magnification (focused on the organic phase to identify microbial growth inside the NAP) and b) a Leica DM40000b AT fluorescence microscope 20x magnification and specific filters sets for alive bacteria (SYTO®9 green-fluorescent nucleic acid stain) and dead bacteria (propidium iodide red-fluorescent nucleic acid stain).
111x54mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Average EC in the 1P-STR (black) and 2P-STR (scratched). Vertical bars represent standard deviations from replicates during steady state in each operational stage. Columns with different letters were significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

75x45mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Time course of CH₄ concentration (black continuous line), the EC (▲, dashed line) and the CO₂ production rate (●, dotted line) during the mass transfer limitation test in a) S1C/S2C (mass transfer limitation scenario), b) S4C (biological limitation scenario).
74x98mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Microscopic images using a phase contrast microscope Leica DM4000b AT of the hydrophobic MOB established in a) S4 (20x magnification), b) S5 (20x magnification) c) S6 (40x magnification) and d) S4 (100x magnification).
84x84mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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DGGE profile of the main bacterial communities present in: the 2P-STR (S3, S4, S5, S6), Initial Inoculum (I) and in the 1P-STR (S3C, S4C, S5C, S6C). The Shannon-Wiener diversity indexes are indicated in the upper part of the gel. The sequenced bands are indicated by "▶" and the corresponding number of each band.
65x76mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Bacterial phylogenetic tree based on neighbor-joining analysis of the 16S rRNA sequences from the enriched populations of both reactors by PCR-DGGE and their closest relatives (similarity > 96%) in GenBank obtained by the Blast search tool. Accession numbers are indicated. Numbers on the nodes indicate bootstrap values (1000 replicates). The scale bar indicates 10% sequence difference.
124x143mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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3 **Comparative performance evaluation of conventional and two-phase**
4 **hydrophobic stirred tank reactors for methane abatement: Mass**
5 **Transfer and Biological Considerations**
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Figure 1:

Figure 1: Time course of the CH₄ loading rate (black continuous line), EC (■, square line) and CO₂ production rate (●, dotted line) during CH₄ biodegradation in the 1P-STR (A) and 2P-STR (B).

Table I: RDP classification of the bacterial DGGE bands, sequences and corresponding matches (Standard Nucleotide BLAST) using the NCBI database, including similarity percentages and sources of origin.

Taxonomic placement (65 % confidence level)	Band n°	Acc. N°	S3	S4	S5	S6	I	S2C	S3C	S4C	S5C	Closest relatives in Blast Name (accession number)	Similarity (%)	Source of origin
Kingdom Bacteria														
Phylum Proteobacteria														
Class <i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>														
Order <i>Rhizobiales</i>														
Family <i>Hyphomicrobiaceae</i>														
Genus <i>Hyphomicrobium</i>	1	KR002620	x									<i>Uncultured bacterium</i> (KJ707339)	96	waste water treatment biofilter
	2	KR002616	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	<i>Hyphomicrobium</i> sp. (FJ711209)	99	Carbonate cave
	3	KR002608	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	<i>Uncultured Hyphomicrobium</i> sp. (JF515535)	98	Soil
Order <i>Rhodoacterales</i>														
Family <i>Rhodobacteraceae</i>														
Genus <i>Stappia</i>	4	KR002610	x	x	x	x		x				<i>Stappia</i> sp. (JF899875)	99	Lake sediment
Class <i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>														
Order <i>Methylococcales</i>														
Family <i>Methylococcaceae</i>														
	5	KR002611	x	x	x		x					<i>Methylomonas rubra</i> (NR_115353)	98	coal mine drainage
	6	KR002612	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> (NR_074627)	98	estuary
	7	KR002607	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	<i>Methylomicrobium album</i> (NR_116197)	94	Soda lake
	8	KR002625		x		x				x	x	<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> (NR074627)	95	seawater
	9	KR002626	x					x	x	x	x	<i>Methylobacter</i> sp.(HF565143)	94	Landfill cover soil
	10	KR002614	x	x								<i>Methylomicrobium album</i> (NR_116196)	94	Soda lake
Genus <i>Methylomonas</i>	11	KR002609	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	<i>Methylomicrobium album</i> (NR_116196)	93	Soda lake
	12	KR002624	x									<i>Methylobacter agile</i> (NR_116197)	93	Soda lake
	13	KR002613		x	x	x						<i>Methylococcus mobilis</i> (NR_104922)	98	sewage sludge
	14	KR002618	x	x	x	x						<i>Methylomonas metanica</i> (NR_074627)	97	Estuary sample
Genus <i>Methylobacter</i>	15	KR002615	x	x								<i>Methylobacter</i> sp.(AY007295.1)	94	Lake
	16	KR002623	x	x								<i>Methylobacter</i> sp.(AY007295.1)	94	Lake
Genus <i>Methylosarcina</i>	17	KR002617	x	x	x							<i>Methylosarcina quisquiliarum</i> (NR_025040)	96	Landfill Soil
	18	KR002619	x	x	x	x						<i>Uncultured bacterium</i> (KF957454)	95	Activated sludge from WWTP
	19	KR002621	x									<i>Methylosarcina lacus</i> (NR_042712)	94	Lake
	20	KR002622	x									<i>Methylosarcina quisquiliarum</i> (NR_025040)	98	Landfill soil
Order <i>Pseudomonadales</i>												<i>Methylosarcina lacus</i> (NR_042712)	97	Lake
Family <i>Pseudomonadaceae</i>												<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.(KP453360)	99	Soil
Order <i>Xanthomonadales</i>														
Family <i>Xanthomonadaceae</i>														
Genus <i>Dokdonella</i>	18	KR002619	x	x	x	x						<i>Uncultured bacterium.</i> (KM886284)	98	Commercial Compost
	19	KR002621	x									<i>Dokdonella ginsengisoli</i> (KF378756)	98	Activated sludge of coking wastewater
Phylum Verrucomicrobia														
Class <i>Verrucomicrobia</i>														
Order <i>Verrucomicrobiales</i>														
Family <i>Spartobacteria</i>														
Genus <i>spartobacteria</i>	19	KR002621	x									<i>Uncultured bacterium</i> (JN868841)	97	Lake water
	20	KR002622	x									<i>Uncultured bacterium</i> (HM129478)	96	Lake
												<i>Uncultured bacterium</i> (JN868841)	99	Lake water
												<i>Uncultured Verrucomicrobium</i> sp.(HQ530642)	97	lake epilimnion

Time course of the CH₄ loading rate (black continuous line), EC (■, square line) and CO₂ production rate (●, dotted line) during CH₄ biodegradation in the 1P-STR (A) and 2P-STR (B).
148x130mm (219 x 219 DPI)

For the first time the viability of methanotrophs inside silicone oil and the optimum cultivation conditions for their enrichment were elucidated. The presence of SO200 influenced the microbial population structure, impacting on bacterial biodiversity and favoring the growth of methanotrophs such as *Methylosarcina*. The

CH_4 abatement performance of the two-phase stirred tank reactor was superior compared with a conventional reactor at high dilution rates due to the retention of the biocatalytic activity inside the NAP.

320x207mm (95 x 95 DPI)